

Interiority Perception: The Actions Within

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We define interiority perception simply as knowledge of the environment within. For primacy of this characteristic to be established and be well-being generating, some care is likely needed. Amongst the most important variables to be identified in this scheme is that the 'outside' is also within. While sensorial predilection favors dichotomy, the notion of interiority perception unifies all impressions as lying 'inside'. The reason being that all frameworks are generated mentally and classificatory delineations, whether causal, spatial, temporal or artefactual are a factor of such origin. In the usual course of our deliberations, we deem and view boundaries as final. Conventional discussion revolves around the significance of individuation and personhood. It might be prudent to shift focus from individuality as origin to solely proper action as emphasis. With action in mind, the reframing of the perception of abundance and deprivation becomes increasingly important. From the locus of the individual, lack or plenty predominantly assume circumstantial dimensions. From the interiority perception perspective that views the outside as also within, there is essentially no determination of divisiveness.

Action is propelled by need and when knowledge of the environment circumvents boundary formation, assessment of quantity is secondary to the realization of value in both presence as well as absence. The generation of expectancy is a derivative of measurement and in the absence of weighing against supposedly fixed parameters, action might be driven by the establishment or re-establishment of focus shorn of evaluation or perhaps even undue definition.

Furthermore, in the perception of a 'total milieu' without characterization through any ascription of inherent nature, a collective field might be purviewed rather than discrete elements that convey impressions of parametric dependence. If this happens, action might be freed of motivational underpinnings that seek gratification or for that matter negation. Thus, the construct of interiority perception might orient towards unbiased action and the equating of even absence as a corollary of an inclusive, collective field. This might prove to be important because, as is known, quantity is instrumental in setting up expectancy. With knowledge of our environment without boundaries, it is possible that absence may be perceived as the signature of intervals between change. With the appreciation of absence without qualification as the hallmark of flux, our actions would indeed effectively be geared towards the reframing of the perception of abundance or lack as well as keep establishing focus on the recognition of value irrespective of individual personhood.